

Factors Influencing Buying Behavior of the Consumers: A Study of Four Wheeler Passenger Tourist Cab State of Uttarakhand

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Abstract

The choices before the customers are increasing rapidly, as more and foreign automobile manufacturers commence operations of India. The market has changed from a sellers' market to a buyers' market. Now new customers are chasing too many goods. As they are getting better products day by day price is no longer considered the single most important factor; rather, other features cast prominence. This study attempts to find out the important features which a customer considers while going to purchase of a new passenger cab. This paper presents the results of the survey of 315 tourists cab's which owner's wants to purchase from potential buyers. This study covers four major cities of the state of Uttarakhand. Result of the study is based on the factor analysis which indicates the nine most important factors considered by buyers while buying a car. These are safety and comfort, Luxury, Economy, Reliability, Fuel Efficiency, Ease of Finance, Variety, Color and Spaciousness, and Brand Image

INTRODUCTION:-

The customer has become very demanding and Companies are facing tough competition to retain the customer satisfaction because there are number of close substitutes which are available in the market. It is very hard for the companies to retain brand loyal customers for a long period of time. It has become very important for the companies to analyze consumer behavior towards their products (Boyd, 1999).

There is nothing strange to say that there are number of factors that influence consumer's buying behavior i.e. cultural, social, personal, psychographic and psychological factors. The consumer develops a set of brand beliefs about where each brand stands on each attribute (Comrey, 1992). Then he forms preferences among the brands in the choice set. The buyer commonly has an intention to buy the most popular brand. Furthermore, decision making varies with the type of buying decision. In case of a high involvement product like an automobile, the product is expensive, frequently was under risky conditions and infrequently bought; complex buying behavior follows, i.e., buyer develops beliefs about the product (Kotler, 2002). He develops an attitude about the product and then makes a well reasoned choice. Thus a marketer needs to develop strategies that assist the buyer in learning about the products' attributes and their relative importance, and which call attention to the high standing of the company's brand on the more important attributes. Therefore, he needs to differentiate the brand's features/ benefits etc. to influence the final brand choice (Malhotra, 2002)

The direct conversation with the buyers and customers and then intercepting their attitudes through surveys, schedules and questionnaires. The collected data had undergone descriptive analysis as used to transform data into understands format and factor analysis was used for identification of factors influencing customer preference. In light of study findings, the preference of a given brand can be explained in terms of six factors namely Product reliability, monetary factor, trendy appeal, frequency of non-price promotions offered, trustworthiness and customer feeling or association towards brand. There is need for marketers to take these factors into consideration when crafting product innovations in the SUV segment of Automobile market (Prasanna Mohan Raj, 2013).

The present research attempts to answer some of the questions regarding brand features of selected cars in India by conducting the market research. These features will help in knowing what a customers or buyer's thinks about a given brand of car and what are the possible factors guiding a possible purchase. Similarly, the idea of measuring the consumer satisfaction will serve the same purpose of determining the customer perception (Nikhil, 2012)

The present paper reviews and analyses the different variables that influence customer purchase intention and also highlights the relationship between variables and their intention to purchase. This study demonstrates that

people care about which country products come from and where they are made and consider these factors when evaluating the quality of product. Stereotypes of country and the preferences of customers, influence the purpose intention. Political system, culture and the economy of the country can be a cause of sensitivity to people. There are many factors that have an impact on consumer purchase intention. Research and methodologies have shown that even when consumers can evaluate all the intrinsic product characteristics by expressing the product, the effect of extrinsic cues has more influence on consumer product evaluation. Country of origin is one of the extrinsic cues; in addition, there is no doubt that country of origin has considerable influence on the purchase intention process Samin Rezvani, Goodarz Javadian Dehkordi, Muhammad Sabbir Rahman 2012)

Objectives

To determine the factors that influences the customers buying behavior of four – wheeler passenger cab.
To study the demographic characteristics of the respondents to their response towards four- wheeler tourist cab.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

The sample of the study is concerned with the consumers / buyers of four-wheeler passenger cabs living in the major cities of the state of Uttarakhand. The selected sample of 315 respondents from the different cities of Uttarakhand i.e. Almora, Nainital Bageshwar and Haridwar was taken by random sampling technique. A non-designed structured questionnaire was prepared for this purpose, which was duly presented and administered personally to the respondents. It was found that all questionnaires had complete responses and thus, the effective number of the respondents was in accordance to the selected...

Table-1.:- Demographic characteristics of respondents.

Age(Years)	Respondents	Percentage
25-35	105	33.4
35-45	122	38.7
45-55	88	27.8
Sex	Respondents	Percentage
Male	295	93.6
Female	20	6.4
Occupation	Respondents	Percentage
Businessmen	135	
Servicemen	78	
Professionals	46	
Others	56	
Income	Respondents	Percentage
<25000	98	
25000-40,4000	109	
>40,000	108	
Education	Respondents	Percentage
Undergraduates	54	
Graduates	156	
Postgraduates	100	
Others	05	
Marital Status	Respondents	Percentage
Married	230	
Unmarrie	85	

Table-2:- Statement showing descriptive statistics:-Analyzing reliability (Cronbach's alpha)

S.N	Statement	Average score	Standard deviation
1	Latest foreign technology vans are always quality products	3.9264	0.7143
2	It would be preferable to buy a best quality vans even at expensive rates	3.7665	0.9254
3	I first look at the reputation of the brand or manufactures goodwill before buying	3.8565	0.7432
4	I would like to buy a van which is recently introduced in the market.	2.8475	1.0574
5	I would like to buy a van whose spare parts are easily available in the market.	4.3451	0.7563
6	Brakes of a van are most critical part to be observed.	4.4523	0.6989
7	I would like to purchase a van on hire purchase system.	3.7682	0.8571
8	Banking system has made the purchase of motor vans for middle class family easy.	4.2342	0.6759
9	Mileage capacity of the van is much important rather than its appearance.	3.9146	1.0432
10	I would like to buy diesel engine van rather than petrol engine van.	3.0143	1.0567
11	Vans having maximum carriage capacity are preferred.	3.8463	0.9751
12	I would like to have a van with good seating capacity and adjustable seats.	3.7588	0.8867
13	Vans should be such that it would be convenient to drive even on rocky and uneven paths.	4.3415	0.6956
14	Vans should be comfortable to drive even for long distance.	4.4432	0.5753
15	Air bags should be standard features of a van.	4.1142	0.6846
16	Doors should have high impact safety bars.	4.2771	0.5958
17	If door is not properly shut warnings lights should flash.	4.1273	0.6339
18	Van should be luxurious and impressive.	4.0867	0.8743
19	Air conditioner should be standard feature of a van.	4.1155	0.7865
20	There should be good service stations and strong dealership.	4.5573	0.5324

Cronbach's alpha =.7531

To find out the factors influencing the buying behavior of the respondents, 20 statements relating to the characteristics of the automobile vans were designed. The respondents were asked to read them and indicate their level of agreement and disagreement on a five point Likert scale where 1 is strongly agrees and 5 strongly disagree. These statements along with their respective average score and standard deviation are shown in table 2. Data so collected was subjected to Factor analysis to bring out the important factors / characteristics of the

vans influencing buying behavior of the sampled respondents. Before applying factors analysis, we will test the reliability of the scale that to which extent the scale produces consistent results. The consistency of result would be obtained by making association between scores obtained from different administrations of the scale. If the association is high, the scale would yield consistent result that would be reliable. Cronbach’s alpha is most widely method which is used allover and its value varies from 0 to 1 but satisfactory value is required to be more than 0.6 for the scale to be reliable in the present study Cronbach, 1951 gave a reliability scale, therefore we have used Cronbach’s alpha scale as measure of reliability. Its value is estimated at .7531(table-2), which indicates high level of scale of reliability.

Table-3 Factors affecting the buying behavior the consumers of tourist van

Factor(variance)	Loading(communalities)	Statement included
1.Safety&Security (9.45%)	.700(.64)	Vans should be such that it would be convenient to drive even on rocky and uneven paths
	.580(.71)	Air bags should be standard features of a van.
	.739(.51)	Doors should have high impact safety bars.
	.549(.79)	If door is not properly shut warnings lights should flash.
2. Comfort (6.39%)	.682(.59)	Van should be luxurious and impressive.
	.585(.72)	Air conditioner should be standard feature of a van.
3. Economic (5.32%)	.762(.68)	Vans having maximum carriage capacity are preferred
	.634(.62)	I would like to buy diesel engine van rather than petrol engine van.
4.Suitability and reliability (6.32)	.424(.62)	Latest foreign technology vans are always quality products

	.709(.649)	There should be good service stations and strong dealership
	.821(.58)	Vans should be comfortable to drive even for long distance
5.Mileage capacity (6.21)	.589(.54)	Brakes of a van are most critical part to be observed
	.722(.67)	Mileage capacity of the van is much important rather than its appearance.
6.Financing facility(6.02)	.775(.56)	Banking system has made the purchase of motor vans for middle class family easy.
	.770(.52)	I would like to purchase a van on hire purchase system
7.Spacious& availability(5.63%)	.498(.69)	I would like to have a van with good seating capacity and adjustable seats.
	.546(.80)	I would like to buy a van whose spare parts are easily available in the market
8.Branding(5.64%)	.538(.68)	It would be preferable to buy a best quality vans even at expensive rates

	.868(.58)	I first look at the reputation of the brand or manufactures goodwill before buying
	.494(.69)	I would like to buy a van which is recently introduced in the market

Result/conclusion:-Consumer behavior consists of all human behavior that goes in making before and post purchase decisions. One can succeed in the competitive market only after understanding the complex consumer behavior. An understanding of the consumer enables a marketer to take marketing decisions which are compatible with its consumer needs. From study there are various major classes of consumer behavior determinants and expectations, namely socioeconomic, psychological, political, geographical, and demographic and Product & Technology. Further classification of human behaviors under main categories will enable car manufacturer to align their strategies in concurrence to customer behavior. While purchasing mini segment car though customer is highly cost conscious but this segment is also upgrading their requirements and due to rise in disposable income, with in segment migration is observed. For mid size segment customer focus is for safety, driving & seating comfort, brand. Also this segment requires value for money, best features and customer friendly vehicles. In higher segment cars like Executive and Premium brand image is main deciding factor which gives assurance of meeting their needs in terms of safety, performance and feature requirements. Global brands are highly preferred in Executive and above segments. So car companies should adopt the “Think-Global, Act-Global”. Approach in strategy making which involves standardization across the world. Brand global presence is judged by consumers based on availability around the globe with standardized products, brand name, distribution channels and communications. By going global, the company will enjoy an increase in market share, which indicates increase in demand for their products. With that, the company can produce with economies of scale, reduce cost per unit and increase production efficiency resulting in serving customers efficiently and economically. Most importantly, compared to local brands, companies with global brands will be able to penetrate into markets more easily, regardless to high or low status seeking consumers, global brands with proper strategy will enable them to achieve an enhanced global image.

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